

ISic3719

I.Sicily inscription 3719

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

stamp

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Sicilia

Place of origin (modern)

Sicily

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, private collection (Manganaro)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI336721

1. M²plough²

2.

3. H

4. ²jar²

5. NIA²retrograde²

6.

7. M|η|víα.

8.

9. εῤ

10. ²amphora²

11.

12. ²dolphin²

13.

14. ²swastika²

15.

16. ²monogram:² Ἡρέα.

17.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 336721

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 51.1395

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